

Program Synthesis from Graded Types (Additional Material)

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This document contains the supplementary material for the paper of the same name which appears in the proceedings for ESOP 2024. Included are the full proofs for the soundness of synthesis and focusing, as well as the collected typing and synthesis calculi.

A Collected Typing Rules

A.1 Typing

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR} \quad \frac{(x : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A')}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma \vdash x : A} \text{DEF} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash t : B}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \lambda x. t : A^r \rightarrow B} \text{ABS} \quad \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma_1 \vdash t_1 : A^r \rightarrow B \quad \Gamma_2 \vdash t_2 : A}{\Sigma; \Gamma_1 + r \cdot \Gamma_2 \vdash t_1 t_2 : B} \text{APP} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : A}{\Sigma; r \cdot \Gamma \vdash [t] : \square_r A} \text{PR} \quad \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A, \Gamma' \vdash t : B \quad r \sqsubseteq s}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_s A, \Gamma' \vdash t : B} \text{APPROX} \\
 \\
 \frac{(C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}')}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma \vdash C : B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}} \text{CON} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : A \quad \Sigma; r \vdash p_i : A \triangleright \Delta_i \quad \Sigma; \Gamma', \Delta_i \vdash t_i : B}{\Sigma; r \cdot \Gamma + \Gamma' \vdash \text{case } t \text{ of } p_1 \mapsto t_1; \dots; p_n \mapsto t_n : B} \text{CASE} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : A[\mu X. A/X]}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : \mu X. A} \mu_1 \quad \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : \mu X. A}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash t : A[\mu X. A/X]} \mu_2 \quad \frac{\bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash t : A}{\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash t : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A} \text{TOPLEVEL}
 \end{array}$$

Fig. A.1: Typing rules

A.2 Pattern Typing

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma; r \vdash x : A \triangleright x :_r A} \text{PVAR} \quad \frac{\Sigma; r \cdot s \vdash p : A \triangleright \Gamma}{\Sigma; r \vdash [p] : \square_s A \triangleright \Gamma} \text{PBOX} \\
\\
\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C : \forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; q_i \cdot r \vdash p_i : B_i \triangleright \Gamma_i \quad |K \bar{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq r \end{array}}{\Sigma; r \vdash C p_1 \dots p_n : K \bar{A} \triangleright \bar{\Gamma}_i} \text{PCON}
\end{array}$$

Fig. A.2: Pattern typing rules

A.3 Kinding

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ty} \quad \Sigma \vdash B : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma \vdash AB : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\text{APP}} \quad \frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma \vdash \square_r A : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\square} \quad \frac{}{\Sigma, \alpha : \kappa \vdash \alpha : \kappa} \kappa_{\text{VAR}} \\
\\
\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty} \quad \Sigma \vdash B : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma \vdash A^r \rightarrow B : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\rightarrow} \quad \frac{}{\Sigma \vdash \text{Unit} : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\text{UNIT}} \quad \frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty} \quad \Sigma \vdash B : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma \vdash A \otimes B : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\otimes} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Sigma \vdash A \oplus B : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\oplus} \\
\\
\frac{}{\Sigma, X : \mathbf{Ty} \vdash X : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_X \quad \frac{\Sigma, X : \mathbf{Ty} \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma \vdash \mu X. A : \mathbf{Ty}} \kappa_{\mu}
\end{array}$$

Fig. A.3: Kinding rules

B Collected Synthesis Calculi

B.1 Collect rules of the synthesis calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{(x : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A')}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma} \text{DEF} \quad \frac{\bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset}{\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset} \text{TOPLEVEL} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \mathbf{Ty}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A} \text{VAR} \quad \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B \Rightarrow \lambda x. t \mid \Delta} \rightarrow_R \\
 \\
 \frac{\begin{array}{c} \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{r_1} B \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \\ \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash A \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \quad \Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \mathbf{Ty} \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash C \Rightarrow [(x_1 t_2)/x_2] t_1 \mid (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2+s_1+(s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B} \rightarrow_L \\
 \\
 \frac{\begin{array}{c} (C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash B_i \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash K \bar{A} \Rightarrow C t_1 \dots t_n \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma + (q_1 \cdot \Delta_1) + \dots + (q_n \cdot \Delta_n)} \text{CR} \\
 \\
 \frac{\begin{array}{c} (C_i : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \mathbf{Ty} \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \\ \exists s_j^i. s_j^i \sqsubseteq s_j^i \cdot q_j^i \sqsubseteq r \cdot q_j^i \quad s_i = s_1^i \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_n^i \quad |K \bar{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r K \bar{A} \vdash B \Rightarrow \text{case } x \text{ of } C_i y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i \mid (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{\sqcup r_i + \sqcup s_i} K \bar{A}} \text{CL} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \square_r A \Rightarrow [t] \mid r \cdot \Delta} \square_R \quad \frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \square_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \square_q A}{\exists s_3. s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q \sqsubseteq r \cdot q \quad \Sigma \vdash \square_q A : \mathbf{Ty}} \square_L \\
 \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r \square_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow \text{case } x \text{ of } [y] \rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_{s_3+s_2} \square_q A \\
 \\
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A[\mu X. A/X] \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \mu X. A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_R \quad \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A[\mu X. A/X] \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r \mu X. A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_L
 \end{array}$$

Fig. B.4: Synthesis rules

The C_L synthesis rule leverages a least-upper bound operation on grades which is given by Definition 3:

Definition 3 (Partial least-upper bound of grades). For two grades r and s of a given semiring, $r \sqcup s$ is defined in terms of the semiring's preorder: $r \sqcup s = t$ if $r \sqsubseteq t$ and $s \sqsubseteq t$ and there exists no other t' where $r \sqsubseteq t'$, $s \sqsubseteq t'$ and $t' \sqsubseteq t$

This operation is lifted pointwise to variable contexts.

C List of Benchmark Synthesis Problems

Data Type		Type Scheme
List	Cons	$\forall a. a^1 \rightarrow \text{List } a^1 \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	Nil	$\forall a. \text{List } a$
Stream	Next	$\forall a. a^1 \rightarrow \text{Stream } a^1 \rightarrow \text{Stream } a$
Bool	True	Bool
	False	Bool
Maybe	Just	$\forall a. a^1 \rightarrow \text{Maybe } a$
	Nothing	$\forall a. \text{Maybe } a$
N	S	$\mathbb{N}^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
	Z	\mathbb{N}
Tree	Node	$\forall a. \text{Tree } a^1 \rightarrow a^1 \rightarrow \text{Tree } a^1 \rightarrow \text{Tree } a$
	Leaf	$\forall a. \text{Tree } a$

Table 3: Data types used in synthesis benchmarking problems

	Problem	Type Scheme
List	append	$\forall a. \text{List } a^1 \rightarrow a^1 \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	concat	$\forall a. \text{List } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	empty	$\forall a. \text{Unit}^1 \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	snoc	$\forall a. \text{List } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	drop	$\forall a. \text{N}^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List}^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	flatten	$\forall a. \text{List } (\text{List } a)^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	bind	$\forall a b. \text{List } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow (a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } b)^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } b$
	return	$\forall a. a^1 \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	inc	$\text{List } \text{N}^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } \text{N}$
	head	$\forall a. \text{List } a^{0..1} \rightarrow a^{0..1} \rightarrow a$
	tail	$\forall a. \text{List } a^{0..1} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	last	$\forall a. \text{List } a^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } a$
	length	$\forall a. \text{List } a \rightarrow \text{N}$
	map	$\forall a b. (a^{1..∞} \rightarrow b)^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } b$
	replicate5	$\forall a. a^5 \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	replicate10	$\forall a. a^{10} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	replicateN	$\forall a. \text{N}^{0..∞} \rightarrow a^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	stutter	$\forall a. \text{List } (a [2])^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{List } a$
	sum	$\text{List } \text{N}^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{N}$
	Stream	build
map		$\forall a b. \text{Stream } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow (a^{1..∞} \rightarrow b)^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{Stream } b$
take1		$\forall a. \text{Stream } a^{0..1} \rightarrow a$
take2		$\forall a. \text{Stream } a^{0..1} \rightarrow (a, a)$
take3		$\forall a. \text{Stream } a^{0..1} \rightarrow (a, (a, a))$
Bool	neg	$\text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	and	$\text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	impl	$\text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	or	$\text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	xor	$\text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
Maybe	bind	$\forall a b. \text{Maybe } a^{1..1} \rightarrow (a^{1..1} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } b)^{0..1} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } b$
	fromMaybe	$\forall a. \text{Maybe } a^{1..1} \rightarrow a^{0..1} \rightarrow a$
	return	$\forall a. a^1 \rightarrow \text{Maybe } a$
	isJust	$\forall a. \text{Maybe } a^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	isNothing	$\forall a. \text{Maybe } a^1 \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	map	$\forall a b. (a^{1..1} \rightarrow b)^{0..1} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } a^{1..1} \rightarrow \text{Maybe } b$
mplus	$\forall a b. \text{Maybe } a^1 \rightarrow \text{Maybe } b^1 \rightarrow \text{Maybe } (a, b)$	
Nat	isEven	$\text{N}^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{Bool}$
	pred	$\text{N}^1 \rightarrow \text{N}$
	succ	$\text{N}^1 \rightarrow \text{N}$
	sum	$\text{N}^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{N}^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{N}$
Tree	map	$\forall a b. (a^{1..∞} \rightarrow b)^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{Tree } a^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{Tree } b$
	stutter	$\forall a. \text{Tree } (a [2])^{1..∞} \rightarrow \text{Tree } (a, a)$
	sum	$\text{Tree } \text{N}^{0..∞} \rightarrow \text{N}$
Misc	compose	$\forall k : \text{Coeffect}, n m : k, a b c : \text{Type}. (a^m \rightarrow b)^n \rightarrow (b^n \rightarrow c)^{1:k} \rightarrow a^{n \cdot m} \rightarrow c$
	copy	$\forall a. a^2 \rightarrow (a, a)$
	push	$\forall k : \text{Coeffect}, c : k, a b : \text{Type}. (a^1 \rightarrow b)^c \rightarrow a^c \rightarrow b [c]$

Table 4: Type schemes for synthesis benchmarking results

D Soundness proofs

Theorem 1 (Soundness). *For all pre-ordered semirings \mathcal{R} :*

1. *For all contexts Γ and Δ , types A , terms t :*

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : A$$

2. *At the top-level, for all type schemes $\forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A$ and terms t then:*

$$\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \emptyset; \emptyset \vdash t : \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A$$

Proof. Induction on the synthesis rules. We consider the cases of the lemma in order, first proving soundness for synthesis of open terms from types, followed by soundness of synthesis for closed term from type schemes.

1. (a) Case VAR

For synthesis of a variable term, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A} \text{VAR}$$

From the premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}$$

from which we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the above conclusion:

$$\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A \vdash x : A} \text{VAR}$$

(b) Case DEF

For synthesis of a top-level definition usage, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{(x : \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A')}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma} \text{DEF}$$

From the premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A')$$

from which we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the above conclusion:

$$\frac{(x : \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A')}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma \vdash x : A} \text{DEF}$$

(c) Case \rightarrow_R

For synthesis of an abstraction term, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B \Rightarrow \lambda x.t \mid \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

By induction on the premise, we have:

$$\Sigma; \Delta, x :_r A \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

and that:

$$r \sqsubseteq q$$

from which we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the conclusion:

$$\frac{\frac{\Sigma; \Delta, x :_r A \vdash t : B \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{\Sigma; \Delta, x :_q A \vdash t : B} \text{APPROX}}{\Sigma; \Delta \vdash \lambda x.t : A^q \rightarrow B} \text{ABS}$$

(d) Case \rightarrow_L

For synthesising an application, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{r_1} B \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash A \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \quad \Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty}}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash C \Rightarrow [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 \mid (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2+s_1+(s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B} \rightarrow_L$$

By induction on the premises, we obtain the following typing judgements:

$$\Sigma; \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \vdash t_1 : C \quad (\text{ih})$$

$$\Sigma; \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash t_2 : A \quad (\text{ih})$$

and from the premises, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty}$$

from which we can construct the following derivation, making use of the admissibility of substitution:

$$\frac{\frac{\Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty}}{\Sigma; x_1 :_1 A^q \rightarrow B \vdash x_1 : A^q \rightarrow B} \text{VAR} \quad \Sigma; \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash t_2 : A}{\Sigma; q \cdot \Delta_2, x_1 :_{1+(q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash x_1 t_2 : B} \text{APP} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{(3) \quad \Sigma; \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \vdash t_1 : C}{\Sigma; (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2+s_1+(s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 : C} \text{SUBST}$$

making use of the distributivity property of semirings, along with unitality of 1 and commutativity of +, such that $s_1 + s_2 \cdot (1 + (q \cdot s_3)) = s_1 + (s_2 \cdot 1) + (s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3) = s_2 + s_1 + (s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)$.

(e) Case C_R

For synthesising a constructor introduction, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C : \forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash B_i \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash K \bar{A} \Rightarrow C t_1 \dots t_n \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma + (q_1 \cdot \Delta_1) + \dots + (q_n \cdot \Delta_n)} \text{C}_R$$

By induction on the premises, we obtain the following typing judgements:

$$\Sigma; \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : B_1 \quad , \dots , \quad \Sigma; \Delta_n \vdash t_n : B_n \quad (\text{ih})$$

from which we can construct the following derivation, matching the above conclusion:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C : \forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \end{array}}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma \vdash C : B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}} \text{CON} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (4) \quad \Sigma; \Delta_1 \vdash t_1 : B_1 \\ \hline \Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma + q_1 \cdot \Delta_1 \vdash C t_1 : B_2^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} \text{ APP} \\ \vdots \\ \hline \Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma + q_1 \cdot \Delta_1 + \dots + q_{n-1} \cdot \Delta_{n-1} \vdash C t_1 \dots t_{n-1} : B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} \text{ APP} \end{array}}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma + q_1 \cdot \Delta_1 + \dots + q_n \cdot \Delta_n \vdash C t_1 \dots t_n : K \bar{A}} \text{APP} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{(5) \quad \Sigma; \Delta_n \vdash t_n : B_n}{\Sigma; 0 \cdot \Gamma + q_1 \cdot \Delta_1 + \dots + q_n \cdot \Delta_n \vdash C t_1 \dots t_n : K \bar{A}} \text{APP}$$

(f) Case C_L

For synthesising a case statement, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C_i : \forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \text{Ty} \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \\ \exists s_j^i. s_j^i \sqsubseteq s_j^i \cdot q_j^i \sqsubseteq r \cdot q_j^i \quad s_i = s_1^i \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_n^i \quad |K \bar{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r K \bar{A} \vdash B \Rightarrow \text{case } x \text{ of } C_i y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i \mid (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{\sqcup r_i + \sqcup s_i} K \bar{A}} \text{C}_L$$

By induction on the premises we obtain the following typing judgements:

$$\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \vdash t_i : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

We have by the definition of \sqcup :

- i. $\Delta_i \sqsubseteq (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m)$
- ii. $r_i \sqsubseteq r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m$

and from the premises of the synthesis rule:

- iii. $s'_j{}^i \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m$
 - iv. $s_j^i \sqsubseteq s'_j{}^i \cdot q_j^i$
 - v. $|K A| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m$
 - vi. $\Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \mathbb{T}y$
- and from rule κ_{\rightarrow} we have that

$$\Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \mathbb{T}y \Rightarrow \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} : \mathbb{T}y$$

thus we have that

- vii. $\Sigma \vdash B_j : \mathbb{T}y$

We then construct the following three derivations towards the goal:

$$\frac{(g)}{\Sigma; q_j^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \vdash y_j^i : B_j \triangleright y_j^i :_{q_j^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_j} \text{PVAR} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} (C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \end{array}}{\Sigma; s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \vdash C_i y_1^i \dots y_n^i : K \bar{A} \triangleright y_j^i :_{q_j^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_j, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_n} \text{PCON} \quad (7)$$

$$(8)$$

and

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \vdash t_i : B}{\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{q_1^i \cdot s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1^i} B_n \vdash t_i : B} \text{INDUCTION} \quad (d)}{\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{q_1^i \cdot s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1^i} B_n \vdash t_i : B} \text{APPROX} \quad (c)}{\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{q_1^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_n \vdash t_i : B} \text{APPROX} \quad (b)}{\Sigma; \Delta_i, x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m)} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{q_1^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_n \vdash t_i : B} \text{APPROX} \quad (a)}{\Sigma; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m)} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{q_1^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{q_n^i \cdot s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m} B_n \vdash t_i : B} \text{APPROX} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\frac{(f)}{\Sigma; x :_1 K \bar{A} \vdash x : K A} \text{VAR} \quad (7) \quad (9)}{\Sigma; ((\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m)} K \bar{A}) + x :_{(s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \cdot 1)} K \bar{A} \vdash \text{case } x \text{ of } C_i y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i : B} \text{CASE} \quad \equiv}{\Sigma; (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m) + (s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m)} K \bar{A} \vdash \text{case } x \text{ of } C_i y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i : B} \equiv$$

- (g) Case \square_R

For synthesising a promotion, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \square_r A \Rightarrow [t] \mid r \cdot \Delta} \square_R$$

By induction on the premise we have:

$$\Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : A$$

From which we can construct the following derivation, matching the above conclusion:

$$\frac{\Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : A}{r \cdot \Delta \vdash [t] : \Box_r A} \text{PR}$$

(h) Case \Box_L

For synthesising an unboxing, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \Sigma; \Gamma, y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \Box_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \Box_q A \\ \exists s_3. s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q \sqsubseteq r \cdot q \quad \Sigma \vdash \Box_q A : \mathbb{T}y \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r \Box_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ [y] \rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_{s_3+s_2} \Box_q A} \Box_L$$

By induction on the premise we have:

$$\Sigma; \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \Box_q A \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

and from the premises we have that:

viii. $s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q$

ix. $\Sigma \vdash \Box_q A : \mathbb{T}y$

and through the κ_{\Box} rule, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash \Box_q A : \mathbb{T}y \Rightarrow \Sigma \vdash A : \mathbb{T}y$$

From this we can construct the following derivation, towards the goal:

$$\frac{(i)}{\Sigma; x :_1 \Box_q A \vdash x : \Box_q A} \text{VAR} \quad (10)$$

$$(10) \frac{\begin{array}{l} \Sigma \vdash A : \mathbb{T}y \\ \frac{\Sigma; s_3 \cdot q \vdash y : A \triangleright y :_{s_3 \cdot q} A}{\Sigma; s_3 \vdash [y] : \Box_q A \triangleright y :_{s_3 \cdot q} A} \text{PBOX} \\ \frac{\Sigma; \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \Box_q A \vdash t : B \quad s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q}{\Sigma; \Delta, y :_{s_3 \cdot q} A, x :_{s_2} \Box_q A \vdash t : B} \text{APPROX} \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Delta, x :_{s_3+s_2} \Box_q A \vdash \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ [y] \rightarrow t : B} \text{CASE}$$

(i) Case μ_R

For synthesising a recursive data type introduction form, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A[\mu X.A/X] \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \mu X.A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_R$$

By induction on the premise we have:

$$D; \Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : A[\mu X.A/X] \quad (\text{ih})$$

from which we can construct the derivation, matching the form of the lemma, leveraging the equirecursivity of our types:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : A[\mu X.A/X]}{D; \Sigma; \Delta \vdash t : \mu X.A} \mu_1$$

(j) Case μL

For synthesising a recursive data type elimination form, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A[\mu X.A/X] \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r \mu X.A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_L$$

By induction on the premise we have:

$$D; \Sigma; \Delta, x :_r A[\mu X.A/X] \vdash t : B \quad (\text{ih})$$

from which we can construct the derivation:

$$\frac{\frac{\Sigma \vdash \mu X.A : \text{Type}}{D; \Sigma; x :_r \mu X.A \vdash x :_1 \mu X.A} \text{VAR}}{D; \Sigma; x :_r \mu X.A \vdash x :_1 A[\mu X.A]} \mu_2$$

and by using lemma 1 on :

$$D; \Sigma; x : A[\mu X.A/X] \vdash t : B$$

we obtain the following, matching the above conclusion:

$$D; \Sigma; D, x : \mu X.A \vdash [x/x]t : B = D; \Sigma; D, x : \mu X.A \vdash t : B$$

2. (a) Case **TOPLEVEL**

For the top-level of synthesis, we have the derivation:

$$\frac{\overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset}{\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset} \text{TOPLEVEL}$$

from induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash t : A \quad (\text{ih})$$

from which we can construct the following typing derivation, matching the above conclusion:

$$\frac{\overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash t : A}{\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash t : \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A} \text{TOPLEVEL}$$

E Focussing

The calculus presented here serves as a starting point for implementing a synthesis algorithm in Granule. However, at the moment the rules are highly non-deterministic with regards the order in which they may be applied. For example, after applying a $\rightarrow R$ rule, we may choose to apply any of the elimination rules before applying an introduction rule for the goal type. This leads to us exploring a large number of redundant search branches which can be avoided through the application of a technique known as *focussing* [4]. Focussing is a tool from linear logic proof theory based on the idea that some rules are invertible, i.e., whenever the conclusion of the rule is derivable, then so are the premises. In other words, the order in which we apply invertible rules doesn't matter. By fixing a particular ordering on the application of invertible rules, we eliminate much of the non-determinism that arises from trying branches which differ only in the order in which invertible rules are applied. We briefly outline focussing and how we apply it.

We begin by augmenting our previous synthesis judgement with an additional context:

$$\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$$

Unlike Γ and Δ , Ω is an *ordered* context. Using the terminology of Andreoli, we refer to rules that are invertible as *asynchronous* and rules that are not as *synchronous* [50]. The intuition here is that asynchronous rules can be applied eagerly, while the non-invertible synchronous rules require us to *focus* on a particular part of the judgement: either on the assumption (if we are in an elimination rule) or on the goal (for an introduction rule). When focussing we apply a chain of synchronous rules, until we either reach a position where no rules may be applied (at which point the branch terminates), we have synthesised a term for our goal, or we have exposed an asynchronous connective at which point we switch back to applying asynchronous rules.

We divide our synthesis rules into four categories, each with their own judgement form, refining the focussing judgement above with an arrow indicating which part of the judgement is currently in focus. An \uparrow indicates an asynchronous phase, and \downarrow a synchronous (focused) phase. The location of the arrow in the judgement indicates whether we are in an introduction or elimination phase:

1. Right Async: $\rightarrow R$ rule with the judgement $\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
2. Left Async: C_L, \square_L rules with the judgement $\Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
3. Right Sync: C_R, \square_R rules with the judgement $\Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
4. Left Sync: $\rightarrow L$ rule with the judgement $\Gamma; \Omega \downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$

We find it helpful to view focussing in terms of a finite state machine, as given in figure E.5. States comprise the four phases of focusing, plus two additional states, FOCUS, and VAR. Edges are then the synthesis rules that direct the transition between focusing phases. The transitions between these focusing phases are handled by dedicated focussing rules for each transition. For the asynchronous

phases, the \uparrow_R/\uparrow_L handle the transition between right to left phases, and left to focusing phases, respectively. Conversely, the \Downarrow_R rule deals with the transition from a right synchronous phase back to a right asynchronous phase, with the \Downarrow_L rule likewise transitioning to a left asynchronous phase. Depending on the current phase of focusing, these rules consider the goal type, the assumption currently being focused on's type, the size of Ω , and the current level of iterative deepening to decide whether to transition between focusing phases. For brevity, we elide the full details here.

Fig. E.5: Focusing State Machine

Appendix E.2 provides the proof of soundness.

E.1 Collected rules of the focusing calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_q A \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash A^q \rightarrow B \uparrow \Rightarrow \lambda x. t \mid \Delta} \rightarrow_R \\
\frac{D; \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}; \emptyset; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset}{D; \emptyset; \emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. A \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset} \text{TOPLEVEL} \\
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad B \text{ not right async}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \uparrow_R
\end{array}$$

Fig. E.6: Right Async rules of the focused fully graded synthesis calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
(C_i : \forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \overline{A}) \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash K \overline{A} : \text{Ty} \\
\Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \overline{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \overline{\alpha} : \overline{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \overline{A}) \\
D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r K \overline{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \overline{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \\
\exists s_j^i. s_j^i \sqsubseteq s_j^i \cdot q_j^i \sqsubseteq r \cdot q_j^i \quad s_i = s_1^i \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_n^i \quad |K \overline{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \\
\hline
D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r K \overline{A} \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \text{case } x \text{ of } \overline{C}_i \ y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i \mid (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m) + (s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m)} K \overline{A} \quad \text{C}_L \\
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r A[\mu X. A/X] \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r \mu X. A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_L \\
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \square_q A}{\exists s_3. s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q \sqsubseteq r \cdot q \quad \Sigma \vdash \square_q A : \text{Ty}} \square_L \\
D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \text{case } x \text{ of } [y] \rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_{s_3 + s_2} \square_q A \\
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad A \text{ not left async}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \uparrow_L
\end{array}$$

Fig. E.7: Left Async rules of the focused fully graded synthesis calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{FOCUS} \\
\frac{D; \Sigma \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad B \text{ not atomic}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \text{FOC}_R \\
\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A; \emptyset \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \text{FOC}_L
\end{array}$$

Fig. E.8: Focus rules of the focused fully graded synthesis calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{(C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}')}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B_i \Downarrow \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i} \text{CONR} \\
 \hline
 D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash K \bar{A} \Downarrow \Rightarrow C t_1 \dots t_n \mid \Delta_1 + \dots + \Delta_n \\
 \\
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \square_r A \Downarrow \Rightarrow [t] \mid r \cdot \Delta} \square_R \\
 \\
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A[\mu X. A/X] \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \mu X. A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_R \\
 \\
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow t \mid \Delta} \Downarrow_R
 \end{array}$$

Fig. E.9: Right Sync rules of the focused fully graded synthesis calculus

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{r_2} B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \quad D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \quad \Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow [(x_1 t_2)/x_2] t_1 \mid (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2 + s_1 + (s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B} \rightarrow_L \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A} \text{VAR} \\
 \\
 \frac{\Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A')}{D, x : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A'; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma} \text{DEF} \\
 \\
 \frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad \text{A not atomic and not left sync}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \Downarrow_L
 \end{array}$$

Fig. E.10: Left Sync, Var, and Def rules of the focused fully graded synthesis calculus

E.2 Soundness

Lemma 2 (Soundness of focusing for graded-base synthesis). *For all contexts Γ , Ω and types A :*

1. RIGHT ASYNC : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \Uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
2. LEFT ASYNC : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
3. RIGHT SYNC : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
4. LEFT SYNC : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
5. FOCUS RIGHT : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$
6. FOCUS LEFT : $D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \iff D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta$

i.e. t has type A under context Δ , which contains variables with grades reflecting their use in t .

Proof. 1. Case: 1. TopLevel:

(a) Case TOPLEVEL

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for abstraction introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}; \emptyset; \emptyset \vdash A \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset}{D; \emptyset; \emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset} \text{TOPLEVEL}$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 1 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the TOPLEVEL synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}; \emptyset \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset}{\emptyset; \emptyset \vdash \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A \Rightarrow t \mid \emptyset} \text{TOPLEVEL}$$

2. Case: 2. Right Async:

(a) Case \rightarrow_R

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for abstraction introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_q A \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash A^q \rightarrow B \uparrow \Rightarrow \lambda x. t \mid \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

By induction on the premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 2 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the \rightarrow_R synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_q A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_r A \quad r \sqsubseteq q}{\Sigma; \Gamma, \Omega \vdash A \rightarrow B \Rightarrow \lambda x. t \mid \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

(b) Case \uparrow_R

In the case of the right asynchronous rule for transition to a left asynchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad B \text{ not right async}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega \vdash B \uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \uparrow_R$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, \Omega \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma.

3. Case 3. Left Async:

 (a) Case CON_L

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for constructor elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C_i : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}) \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \text{Ty} \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}) \\ D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \\ \exists s_j^i. s_j^i \sqsubseteq s_j^i \cdot q_j^i \sqsubseteq r \cdot q_j^i \quad s_i = s_1^i \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_n^i \quad |K \bar{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \end{array}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r K \bar{A} \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ C_i \ y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i \mid (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m) + (s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m)} K \bar{A}} \text{C}_L$$

By induction on the second premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From the second premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \text{Ty}$$

From which we can construct the following instantiation of the CON_L rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C_i : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}) \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash K \bar{A} : \text{Ty} \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}) \\ \Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{r \cdot q_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{r \cdot q_n^i} B_n \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i, x :_{r_i} K \bar{A}, y_1^i :_{s_1^i} B_1, \dots, y_n^i :_{s_n^i} B_n \\ \exists s_j^i. s_j^i \sqsubseteq s_j^i \cdot q_j^i \sqsubseteq r \cdot q_j^i \\ s_i = s_1^i \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_n^i \quad |K \bar{A}| > 1 \Rightarrow 1 \sqsubseteq s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m \end{array}}{\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r K \bar{A} \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ C_i \ y_1^i \dots y_n^i \mapsto t_i \mid (\Delta_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup \Delta_m), x :_{(r_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup r_m) + (s_1 \sqcup \dots \sqcup s_m)} K \bar{A}} \text{CON}_L$$

 (b) Case \square_L

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for graded modality elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \square_q A \\ \exists s_3. s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q \sqsubseteq r \cdot q \quad \Sigma \vdash \square_q A : \text{Ty} \end{array}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ [y] \rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_{s_3 + s_2} \square_q A} \square_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \square_q A \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From the third premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash \square_q A : \text{Ty}$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the \square_L synthesis rule in the non focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} \Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), y :_{r \cdot q} A, x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta, y :_{s_1} A, x :_{s_2} \square_q A \\ \exists s_3. s_1 \sqsubseteq s_3 \cdot q \sqsubseteq r \cdot q \quad \Sigma \vdash \square_q A : \text{Ty} \end{array}}{\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r \square_q A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow \mathbf{case} \ x \ \mathbf{of} \ [y] \rightarrow t \mid \Delta, x :_{s_3 + s_2} \square_q A} \square_L$$

(c) Case μ_L

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for recursive data type elimination, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r A[\mu X.A/X] \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r \mu X.A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r A[\mu X.A/X] \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the μ_L synthesis rule in the non focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r A[\mu X.A/X] \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{\Sigma; (\Gamma, \Omega), x :_r \mu X.A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_L$$

(d) Case \uparrow_L

In the case of the left asynchronous rule for transitioning an assumption from the focusing context Ω to the non-focusing context Γ , the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A; \Omega \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad \text{A not left async}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \Omega, x :_r A \uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \uparrow_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, x : A, \Omega \vdash C \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma.

4. Case 4. Right Sync:

(a) Case CON_R

In the case of the right synchronous rule for constructor introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B_i \Downarrow \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash K \bar{A} \Downarrow \Rightarrow C t_1 \dots t_n \mid \Delta_1 + \dots + \Delta_n} \text{CON}_R$$

By induction on the second premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash B_i \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the CON_R synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} (C : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}) \in D \\ \Sigma \vdash B_1^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A} = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. B_1'^{q_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow B_n'^{q_n} \rightarrow K \bar{A}') \\ \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash B_i \Rightarrow t_i \mid \Delta_i \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash K \bar{A} \Rightarrow C t_1 \dots t_n \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma + (q_1 \cdot \Delta_1) + \dots + (q_n \cdot \Delta_n)} \text{CON}_R$$

(b) Case \square_R

In the case of the right synchronous rule for graded modality introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{\Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \square_r A \Downarrow \Rightarrow [t] \mid r \cdot \Delta} \square_R$$

By induction on the premises, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the μ_R synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \square_r A \Rightarrow [t] \mid r \cdot \Delta} \square_R$$

(c) Case μ_R

In the case of the right synchronous rule for recursive data type introduction, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A[\mu X.A/X] \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash \mu X.A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_R$$

By induction on the premises, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A[\mu X.A/X] \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the μ_R synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A[\mu X.A/X] \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma \vdash \mu X.A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \mu_R$$

(d) Case \Downarrow_R

In the case of the right synchronous rule for transitioning from the right focusing phase to an asynchronous right phase, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Uparrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow t \mid \Delta} \Downarrow_R$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 4 of the lemma.

5. Case 5. Left Sync:

(a) Case \rightarrow_L

In the case of the left synchronous rule for application, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B; x_2 :_{r_1} B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \\ \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B; \emptyset \vdash A \Downarrow \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \\ \Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty} \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \Downarrow \vdash C \Rightarrow [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 \mid (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2+s_1+(s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B} \rightarrow_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{r_1} B \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B$$

from case 5 of the lemma. By induction on the second premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash A \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 4 of the lemma. From the third premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty}$$

From which, we can construct the following instantiation of the \rightarrow_L synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{r_1} B \vdash C \Rightarrow t_1 \mid \Delta_1, x_1 :_{s_1} A^q \rightarrow B, x_2 :_{s_2} B \\ \Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash A \Rightarrow t_2 \mid \Delta_2, x_1 :_{s_3} A^q \rightarrow B \\ \Sigma \vdash A^q \rightarrow B : \text{Ty} \end{array}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x_1 :_{r_1} A^q \rightarrow B \vdash C \Rightarrow [(x_1 t_2)/x_2]t_1 \mid (\Delta_1 + s_2 \cdot q \cdot \Delta_2), x_1 :_{s_2+s_1+(s_2 \cdot q \cdot s_3)} A^q \rightarrow B} \rightarrow_L$$

(b) Case VAR

In the case of the left synchronous rule for variable synthesis, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A} \text{VAR}$$

From the premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}$$

from which, we can construct the following instantiation of the VAR synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}}{\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma, x :_1 A} \text{VAR}$$

(c) Case DEF

In the case of the left synchronous rule for synthesis of a top-level definition usage, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{\Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A')}{D, x : \forall \bar{\alpha} : \bar{\kappa}. A'; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \Downarrow \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma} \text{DEF}$$

From the premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma \vdash A : \text{Ty}$$

from which, we can construct the following instantiation of the VAR synthesis rule in the non-focusing calculus:

$$\frac{(x : \forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. A') \in D \quad \Sigma \vdash A = \text{inst}(\forall \alpha : \bar{\kappa}. A')}{\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash A \Rightarrow x \mid 0 \cdot \Gamma} \text{DEF}$$

(d) Case \Downarrow_L

In the case of the left synchronous rule for transitioning from the right focusing phase to an asynchronous left phase, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad A \text{ not atomic and not left sync}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \Downarrow_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 5 of the lemma.

6. Case 6. Right Focus:

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a right synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \vdash B \Downarrow \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad B \text{ not atomic}}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \text{FOC}_R$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma \vdash C \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma.

7. Case 7. Left Focus:

In the case of the focusing rule for transitioning from a left asynchronous judgement to a left synchronous judgement, the synthesis rule has the form:

$$\frac{D; \Sigma; \Gamma; x :_r A \Downarrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta}{D; \Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A; \emptyset \Uparrow \vdash B \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta} \text{FOC}_L$$

By induction on the first premise, we have that:

$$\Sigma; \Gamma, x :_r A \vdash C \Rightarrow t \mid \Delta \quad (\text{ih})$$

from case 3 of the lemma.